

DISTANCE EDUCATION IN THE SYSTEM OF MODERN HIGHER PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Modern society is characterized by a new view of education, which modifies the functional role of the education system and gives it the character of an integrative social institution. The processes of globalization of all spheres of public life make the implementation of the task of continuous education of the population with a vital necessity.*

Key words: *development of education, distance learning, development, knowledge, information, communication, professional activity.*

The target program for the development of education provides for "the introduction of new educational technologies and the principles of the organization of the educational process, ensuring the effective implementation of new educational models of continuous education, including using modern information and communication technologies." Innovative educational technologies include distance learning. Modern distance educational technologies (DET) open up real prospects for improving the quality of knowledge and efficiency of the educational process, for solving various social problems associated with the functioning of the Institute of Education.

Distance learning is a universal humanistic form of training, based on the use of a wide range of traditional, new information and telecommunication technologies, and technical means that create conditions for a trained free choice of educational disciplines that meet standards, dialogue exchange with a teacher, while the learning process does not depend from the location of the student in space and in time.

Remote educational technologies are understood to mean educational technologies, implemented mainly with the use of information and telecommunication technologies with mediated (at a distance) or not completely mediated interaction of a student and pedagogical worker. It is able to satisfy the needs for education, increase the human capital of representatives of all social groups and layers. But it acquires special

significance for residents of settlements remote from university centers, for those who, due to various circumstances (motherhood, disability, unemployment, employment, a large break between the previous education, etc.) cannot be educated according to traditional technology. In the context of the formation of a system of continuous education and continuing education, distance learning becomes an optimal form of advanced learning and professional retraining.

The development of distance education requires a special scientific study of two key, interconnected problems of vocational education - its social accessibility and quality. Distance education provides a wide range of higher school services in basic and additional programs and forms of training for various sections of the population in conditions of innovative development. Therefore, it has significant social potential. In this regard, the strategic goal of distance education is the provision of the possibility of obtaining a quality education of any level at the place of residence or professional activity to various social groups and layers, regardless of living conditions and work in accordance with individual capabilities and abilities.

Remote education allows you to combine the place of work and study, save the time of training through the effective use of information and communication technologies (ICT). The effectiveness of distance education from the point of view of the quality of knowledge and its demand in the market, most students are evaluated no lower than the traditional educational process. The widespread implementation of distance education will expand access to the formation of various segments of the population, including not having the necessary financial and other resources to obtain traditional education.

Possessing advantages such as flexibility, modality, parallelism, wide coverage, profitability, technological, access to world information resources, etc., with the corresponding scientific and methodological organization, distance learning will ensure a high level of knowledge and thereby take a favorable position in the educational services market. Distance learning can become an effective means of ensuring a leading vocational education, which is by nature innovative.

Today, the relevant task is not so much the propaganda of distance education as the elimination of negative factors accompanying this type of education. Our analysis of distance educational services in universities allows us to distinguish two main interconnected social problems - improving quality and ensuring the social availability of these services. The

solution of one of them involves the solution of the second problem. Improving the quality of distance education will eliminate discrediting factors, among which the "easily accessibility" of higher education is in the first place - the ability, using distance educational services for a relatively moderate fee, get a diploma of higher education, without applying special intellectual efforts. In contrast to "easily accessibility", social accessibility involves the alignment of social chances of obtaining higher education of the corresponding quality.

However, qualitative education has always been and will remain an object of social competition, since it is such an education, along with other factors, that provides good initial opportunities for individuals. There will always be acute not only intellectual, but also social competition for places in prestigious universities in prestigious specialties and areas of training. From the point of view of sociology, it is important to study the interest of the main participants in the educational process - universities, students, applicants and their parents, employers, state bodies - in improving the quality of education. The main social mechanism for improving the quality of distance educational services is the integration of interested participants in the educational process. Such integration is possible only when the extraction of not one-sided, but mutual benefits - universities, consumers of services, employers, and the state become obvious. This requires stable communications between participants in the educational process. There are no ready-made proposals for improving the quality of distance education, since this is a multifaceted problem that requires a constant solution. Distance training is a new technology for the organization of the educational process, which is based on the principle of independent training and is expressed in the purposeful process of interactive interaction of teachers and students using information and telecommunication technologies that provide students with the necessary volume of educational material.

Modern distance educational technologies open up real prospects for improving the quality of knowledge and efficiency of the educational process, for solving various social problems associated with the functioning of the institute of education. Remote educational services can satisfy the needs for education, increase the human potential of representatives of all social groups and layers.

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